

This document is the Accepted Manuscript version of a Published Work after peer review and technical editing by the publisher that appeared in final form in [Trends in Analytical Chemistry, 26 (2007) 239-251], To access the final edited and published work see [<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2007.01.004>].

Determination of pesticide residues in olive oil and olives

Juan F. García-Reyes, Carmen Ferrer, M. José Gómez-Ramos, Antonio Molina-Díaz, Amadeo R. Fernández-Alba

Juan F. García-Reyes, Carmen Ferrer, M. José Gómez-Ramos, Amadeo R. Fernández-Alba*
Pesticide Residue Research Group, Department of Hydrogeology and Analytical Chemistry,
University of Almería, 04120 La Cañada de San Urbano, Almería, Spain

Juan F. García-Reyes, Antonio Molina-Díaz
Department of Physical and Analytical Chemistry, University of Jaén, 23071 Jaén, Spain

*Corresponding author. Tel.: +34 950 015034; Fax: +34 950 015084; E-mail: amadeo@ual.es

ABSTRACT

Pesticide-residue determination in olive oil is becoming a very important and challenging issue. The present article provides a review of the most significant methods for determining pesticides in olive oil. The discussion of sample-treatment procedures is focused on not only the final product (olive oil), but also the direct analysis of the raw material (olive fruits). We outline extraction and clean-up procedures (e.g., liquid-liquid partition, gel-permeation chromatography (GPC), solid-phase extraction (SPE), matrix solid-phase dispersion (MSPD) and Quick, Easy, Cheap, Effective, Rugged and Safe (QuEChERS). However, we pay specially attention to the clean-up stage, which plays an important role in the whole process.

In addition, identification and quantitation of pesticides have been carried out by gas chromatography (GC) coupled to different detectors (flame-ionization (FID), nitrogen-phosphorus (NPD) and electron-capture (ECD), although either GC-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) in selected ion monitoring (SIM) mode or GC-tandem MS (GC-MS²) are becoming the combination of choice, because of higher selectivity and confirmation capabilities. In recent years, the appearance of new, more polar pesticides has prompted the use of liquid chromatography-MS (LC-MS) instead of GC-MS, and we outline its advantageous features for the analyses of polar pesticides in olive oil.

Keywords: Chromatography; Food safety; Mass spectrometry; Olive oil; Pesticide

Abbreviations: APCI, Atmospheric pressure chemical ionization; ECD, Electron-capture detector; ESI, Electrospray ionization; FID, Flame-ionization detector; GC, Gas chromatography; GC-IT-MS², GC-MS² using an ion-trap analyzer; GC-Q-MS, GC-MS using a single-quadrupole analyzer; GC-QqQ-MS², GC-MS² using a triple-quadrupole analyzer; GPC, Gel-permeation chromatography; LC, Liquid chromatography; LC-IT-MS², LC-MS² using an ion-trap analyzer; LC-Q-MS, LC-MS using a single-quadrupole analyzer; LC-QqQ-MS², LC-MS² using a triple-quadrupole analyzer; LC-TOF-MS, LC-MS using a time-of-flight (TOF) analyzer; MS, Mass spectrometry; MS², Tandem mass spectrometry; MSPD, Matrix solid-phase dispersion; NPD, Nitrogen-phosphorus detector; SIM, Selected ion monitoring; SPE, Solid-phase extraction; SRM, Selected reaction monitoring; TOTAD, "Through oven transfer adsorption desorption" interface

1. Introduction

Olive oil is a very important commodity in the Mediterranean Basin. This product has a great importance in the sustainable economy of important regions in Spain, Greece and Italy – the main olive oil producers in the world. Virgin olive oil is obtained from the fruit of the olive tree (*Olea Europaea*) exclusively by mechanical and/or physical means without any further treatment under thermal conditions that do not alter the olive-oil quality. It is the main ingredient of the Mediterranean Diet, since it possesses highly beneficial nutritional and culinary properties due to its unique composition in containing fatty acids and antioxidants. The benefits of olive oil to health [1] have prompted a demand for this product worldwide [2] (Fig. 1).

In order to avoid possible losses at harvest or in production, due mainly to insect attack, several agrochemicals are applied to olive groves. Their residues in olive oil constitute an important parameter of its quality; they must be monitored regularly and kept as low as possible to ensure consumer protection [3].

The most extensively applied agrochemicals in olive plantations of Mediterranean countries are insecticides, herbicides and fungicides. The residues of these pesticides can persist to the harvest stage, so they may contaminate the olives used to produce olive oil. This can cause the presence of trace amounts of these pesticides in olive-oil samples. Furthermore, the appearance of new cost-effective has led to herbicides residues being present in both olives and olive oil.

For these reasons, different regulations establishing maximum residue limits (MRLs) in olives and olive oil have been established by both the European Union and the Codex Alimentarius Commission of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) [2,4]. In addition, new regulations will be established in the years ahead for pesticide residues in olive oil with MRLs of the same order as baby food (10 µg/kg) [5,6].

In addition, the new emerging field of “organic food” requires the development of tools to analyze pesticide residues (viz. in olive oil with “organic food” label) at very low-µg/kg concentration levels (i.e. 0.5–2 µg/kg).

Monitoring pesticide residues in olive oil is therefore of great interest to ensure “food safety” in terms of pesticide-residue levels. For this task, the development of multi-residue methods, which allow proper control of a large number of pesticides in a unique analysis, is the most common strategy. However, the different classes and physicochemical properties make it difficult to develop methodologies that cover all the analytes under study. Sometimes, different sample-treatment methodologies are

necessary.

The analysis of pesticide residues in olive oil is very challenging, because of the inherent complexity of the matrix, mainly comprising triglycerides (98–99%). This drives the need for different strategies to isolate or to extract the pesticide fraction from the whole fatty matrix [7]. In fact, it is very difficult to avoid co-extraction of fatty material, even more so taking into account that some of the pesticides usually studied are fat-soluble non-polar compounds (viz. organochlorine); they tend to concentrate and remain in the fat. Since high recoveries of most multi-class pesticides (which have a wide range of very different physicochemical properties) must be obtained in a (ideally) fat-free extract, to avoid damage to the different parts of the instruments used and potential interferences in the chromatographic analysis, an additional clean-up step is necessary prior to subsequent steps in the analytical process.

Sample preparation is therefore a crucial step in the analytical procedure since even small amount of lipids can harm columns and detectors or suppress signal. Many multi-residue procedures employ different clean-up techniques and a variety of detection methods for the determination of pesticide residues in olive oil. The most common methodology is based on gas chromatography (GC) after a comprehensive clean-up step, mostly based on liquid-liquid partitioning or gel-permeation chromatography (GPC) to separate the low-molecular-mass pesticides from the higher molecular-mass fat constituents of the oil, such as triglycerides.

However, analytical determination is less problematic than the sample-treatment step, especially with the advent and the huge development in coupling gas or liquid chromatography to mass spectrometry (GC-MS and LC-MS). This review covers the main methodologies for the determination of pesticides in olive oil, involving not only the determination but also the sample-treatment and extraction procedure, which is the key step and the bottleneck in this kind of analysis.

The discussion of sample-treatment procedures is focused not only on the final product (olive oil) but also on direct analysis of the raw material (olive fruits).

We critically discuss and evaluate the different approaches employed for the extraction of pesticides – liquid-liquid extraction (LLE), GPC, matrix solid-phase dispersion (MSPD), reversed-phase LC (RPLC) or solid-phase extraction (SPE) – paying special attention to the clean-up stage, which plays an important role in the whole process. Moreover, we outline the identification and the quantitation of pesticides, which has been carried out by gas chromatography (GC) coupled to different detectors – flame ionization (FID), nitrogen-phosphorus (NPD), electrochemical (ECD), GC-MS in selected-ion monitoring (SIM) mode or GC-MS².

Finally, the appearance and the use of new polar pesticides has prompted the use of LC-MS instead of GC-MS. We will detail the advantageous features of LC-MS methods for the analyses of polar pesticides in olive oil.

2. Sample treatment and extraction

The development of sample-treatment procedures for the isolation of pesticides in samples with relatively high fat content (i.e. >15%), such as olive oil and olives, is demanding. The preparation of oil samples for the determination of pesticides by chromatographic techniques requires the complete removal of the high-molecular-mass fat from the sample to maintain the chromatographic system in working order. The main problem associated when working with this kind of matrices is that dirty extracts with even small amounts of fat may harm the whole system (columns and detectors). For this reason, an additional clean-up step is usually included in these methods.

In addition, the development of “multi-residue” methods to control a large number of compounds is highly desirable. However, the different natures and physicochemical properties of the classes of compounds to be studied (e.g., organochlorines, organophosphorus and triazines) makes it even more complex to establish extraction methodologies.

In this sense, the fat solubility of pesticides applied to olives intended for oil production is an important parameter that must be considered. It has been demonstrated that fat-soluble pesticides tend to concentrate in olive oil during its production and extraction from the olives at concentration factors in the range 1.5–5 [4]. For this reason, higher concentration levels of fat-soluble insecticides are expected in the oil than in the olives from which the oil was produced. As an indication of fat solubility, the logarithm of the partition coefficient between octanol and water ($\log K_{o/w}$) is used. By contrast, polar pesticides applied to olives do not tend to preconcentrate in the olive-oil phase during its production, so their levels are not expected to be as high as in olive samples. Together with the preconcentration factor of selected fat-soluble pesticides in olive oil, the matrix also stabilizes and protects them from degradation or oxidation phenomena, thus making possible the persistence of these compounds even at low concentration levels for long periods [4].

2.1. Extraction procedures for olive oil

Many multi-residue procedures employing different clean-up techniques and a variety of detection methods have been reported for the determination of pesticide residues in olive oil. A summary of most of these methods is included in Table 1 [8–42]. In most cases, the extraction methods are based on one of the following methodologies:

- gel-permeation chromatography (GPC), with or without a preliminary liquid-liquid partition step;
- solid-phase extraction (SPE) methodologies, with or without a preliminary liquid-liquid partition step; and,
- liquid-liquid partition and other methodologies

2.1.1. GPC. To date, GPC is the most extensively used technique in routine laboratories for the analysis of pesticides residues in olive oil, generally after a preliminary liquid-liquid partition with acetonitrile, using GC analysis with different detectors (ECD, NPD and MS) [8–13], although there are methods based on direct extraction and clean-up of pesticides from olive oil without a liquid-liquid partition step, using only GPC [12]. However, to lengthen the life of the columns and chromatographic systems – in both extraction and determination steps – and to obtain cleaner extracts, we strongly recommend performing the partitioning step prior to GPC. Fig. 2(a) shows the experimental set-up required for a GPC method.

An aliquot of, and olive-oil extract from, the preliminary partitioning step (i.e. olive oil – dissolved in hexane saturated with acetonitrile – with acetonitrile saturated with hexane) is injected into the GPC system. The selected fraction is collected and, after a solvent-exchange step, the sample is injected [10]. These GPC systems comprise a HPLC pump, a fraction collector and a detector (optional). The columns are made from polymeric porous microspheres, which enable the separation of compounds according to their molecular weights. Using this principle, the pesticide fraction is separated from the high molecular-weight triglyceride fractions. The compounds are eluted from higher to lower molecular weight. Prior to analysis, the collection time is selected using molecular weight markers in order to calibrate the column.

These methods provide good recovery rates for a large number of pesticides used in an olive grove and can be easily implemented – at least the GPC step – in an automated fashion, using appropriate software and a fraction collector. The high degree of automation is therefore the key advantage of this method, particularly compared with other manual methods (e.g., SPE). By contrast, it is difficult to set optimized conditions to discriminate fully between the pesticide fraction and the rest of components from such a fatty matrix, comprising mainly triglycerides, since both fractions partially overlap. Normally, the

fractionation time interval is selected in order to yield a clean extract although some of the pesticides under study will not be fully recovered. In addition, the acquisition and maintenance costs of the instrument and the large amount of toxic solvents consumed per analysis are important drawbacks of this methodology.

It is therefore necessary to develop a new extraction procedure with lower reagent and solvent consumption and without an expensive instrument. It is desirable to find new, effective and fast methodologies that involve little cost, using only disposable chemicals or sorbents and yielding clean extracts and good recovery rates.

2.1.2. SPE. As an alternative to GPC, other options involving the use of various SPE-based procedures – in both extraction and clean-up steps – have been described for the analyses of pesticide residues in olive oil (see [Table 1](#)) [15–29].

These procedures usually comprise a preliminary liquid-liquid partition step – although there are methods without this step – followed by one or more stages of extraction and clean-up, using different sorbents (e.g., Florisil, alumina, aminopropyl, graphitized carbon black or silica gel) and employing different methodologies (e.g., SPE [15], SPME [20] or MSPD [28]). Different methods based on SPE have been described, comprising either a unique step using different sorbents for extraction and clean-up [15–19,21] or a combination of a preliminary liquid-liquid partitioning stage followed by SPE clean-up [22–27]. The results obtained with these techniques are fully satisfactory, yielding high recovery rates and clean extracts with lower consumption of organic solvents. By contrast, these methods are time-consuming and laborious, with several manual stages.

Recently, an MSPD-based method was described for the analyses of pesticides in both olives and olive oil [28,29]. As can be seen in [Fig. 2\(b\)](#), MSPD is an SPE- based strategy, in which a fine dispersion of the matrix is mixed with a sorbent material (e.g., silica, alumina or C₁₈) with a mortar and a pestle. Prior to the MSPD step, a preliminary liquid-liquid partitioning step is performed using acetonitrile saturated with petroleum ether. The extract obtained is blended with aminopropyl, and, after that, this material is packed into a minicolumn, where the analytes are eluted by a relatively small volume of a suitable eluting solvent. This step can be accomplished together with a “co-column” clean-up to achieve a further degree of matrix removal. The co-column material (Florisil or silica, in the example) is packed into the bottom of the same column of the sorbent, cleaning the sample as it elutes from the MSPD sorbent-matrix mixture. MSPD therefore enables the development of straightforward extraction and clean-up steps, reducing the use of large amount of toxic solvents and speeding up the sample-treatment process. The MSPD procedure is schematically depicted in [Fig. 2\(b\)](#). Aminopropyl was used as MSPD

sorbent and a final clean-up step was performed using a column packed with Florisil in the elution step. This MSPD method consumes little reagent consumption, generates little waste, and avoids the use of expensive GPC manifolds. Furthermore, the resultant extracts are cleaner than those usually obtained by GPC as can be seen in Fig. 3, where a full-scan GC-MS olive-oil-matrix chromatogram obtained using GPC is compared with that obtained by partitioning with acetonitrile followed by MSPD. This illustrates the capabilities of the MSPD method to provide clean extracts of such complex matrixes with high fat content. In addition, recoveries of 73–130% and RSD values below 10% were obtained in olive oil at different fortification levels. However, as stated before, the main pitfall is the lack of automation and the total time of analysis – including partitioning and MSPD stages – in the olive-oil procedure.

2.1.3. Liquid-liquid partitioning and other methodologies. Nowadays, most of the methods described for the analyses of pesticides in olive oil include a clean-up stage, since the extracts obtained after partitioning contain certain amounts of fat. However, some years ago, there was a more basic approach that is still used [30–34]. A very simple multi-residue method for 13 organophosphorus insecticides [34], based only on hexane-acetonitrile partitioning, obtained remarkably good recoveries of 74–118%. Dugo et al. described a method for organophosphorus pesticides in olive oil based on partitioning with acetonitrile and centrifugation [31]. However, these approaches shorten the life-time of both columns and the chromatographic system, and further clean-up of extracts is mandatory.

Together with the methods described above based on both GPC and SPE, there are shorter extraction methods (e.g., supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) [14] or the development of on-line coupling to accomplish extraction, clean-up and chromatographic determination in the same stage). These methods are based on coupling reversed-phase liquid chromatography (RPLC) with gas chromatography (RPLC-GC) by means of a total oven transfer adsorption-desorption (TOTAD) interface [35–38] or direct coupling of GPC with gas chromatography (GPC-GC) [39,40].

2.2. Extraction procedures for olives

In the case of olives, there are few methodologies for the extraction of pesticides. The sample must be fully homogenous. Different extraction procedures based on SPE and GPC methodology are included in Table 1.

2.2.1. Liquid-liquid partitioning followed by clean-up step with GPC or SPE. The blended

olive sample is mixed with anhydrous sodium sulphate in order to remove water from the olives, and, after that, is extracted twice with petroleum ether, with the aid of a high-speed blender (i.e. Ultraturrax) [41]. The extract obtained is purified by means of the same GPC or SPE procedures employed for olive oil. Recently, a combined approach based on low-temperature (-20 °C) lipid removal and SPE clean-up with alumina was proposed [42].

2.2.2. Direct MSPD. The same MSPD procedure described above for olive oil can be extended to olives. In fact, the preliminary partitioning step is removed from the procedure, therefore simplifying and speeding up the analysis time [28]. 1 g of crushed and homogenized olives is gently blended in a glass mortar with 2 g of aminopropyl, and, after that, the clean-up process is performed in the elution step, as with olive-oil samples. The results are fully satisfactory with good recovery rates for different classes of pesticides and, compared with other partitioning methods, simpler and faster. In addition, the reagent consumption is much lower than GPC methods.

2.3. Recent developments

A “Quick, Easy, Cheap, Rugged and Safe” (QuEChERS) method, described by Anastassiades et al. [43] and based on liquid-liquid partitioning with acetonitrile followed by a clean-up step with dispersive SPE, was recently explored for the analyses of pesticides in both olives and olive oil (Fig. 2©) [44]. This method is slightly different from the general procedure applicable to fruits and vegetables with lower fat content. The main difference is the clean-up step, where a mixture of different sorbents (C₁₈, primary secondary amine (PSA) and graphitized carbon black (GCB)) is used instead of PSA alone. Preliminary results are promising with good recovery rates for most of the pesticides [44]. Only less polar pesticides (e.g., organochlorines) suffer from poor recovery percentages (below 70%). The extracts obtained are clean enough to perform GC-MS and/or LC-MS² analyses. The main advantages of this method are its simplicity, the use of cheap disposable reagents and materials, the small volume of organic solvent consumed and the large number of samples – over 10 – that can be processed in an hour. This procedure for pesticide determination in both olives and olive oil will be used in future.

The tendency of the extraction methods in both olive oil and olives is moving towards development of single, cost-effective, high-throughput methodologies that yield clean extracts and good recoveries for hundreds of multi-class pesticides (to be suitable for multi-residue determination methods using state-of-the-art MS methods), and reduction in the

total volume of organic solvents consumed – environmentally friendly extraction procedures. QuEChERS provides these key features, being well- suited to use as an extraction procedure in multi-residue methods for pesticide determination in fatty matrices, such as olives and olive oil.

3. Identification and quantitation

The identification of pesticides in foodstuffs with high fat content is a difficult task, which requires selective techniques for unambiguous confirmation, since interfering species from the matrix often mask the signal of the target compounds. For these reasons, the use of chromatographic techniques coupled with MS detection is highly desirable in order to attain satisfactory results. These techniques enable unequivocal identification and confirmation of target species, unlike less selective detectors (e.g., NPD and ECD), avoiding matrix interferences and both false positives and false negatives.

To date, the most widely used approach for the analyses of pesticide residues in olive oil has been GC-MS. MS detection systems have replaced formerly used selective detection systems (e.g., NPD and ECD) [4]. In fact, according to the guidelines proposed by SANCO [45], these detectors do not provide enough selectivity to confirm the presence of a substance. The use of MS techniques is mandatory to obtain unambiguous identification. In this sense, the EU has established an identification criterion for contaminants, which involves the use of MS techniques in order to meet the confirmation criteria, based on the use of identification points (a different number of points is assigned according to the type of MS detection used (e.g., MS², high resolution, or SIM mode) [46].

3.1. GC-MS

The use GC-MS is particularly suited to the analysis of volatile and non-polar compounds. MS detectors provide enough selectivity to detect pesticide residues in both olives and olive-oil samples at low concentration levels. There are various techniques in GC-MS. Nowadays, the most widely extended technique in routine laboratories for pesticide-residue analysis (PRA) is GC-MS using a quadrupole analyzer in SIM mode. It enables appropriate limits of detection (LODs), in compliance with the regulations established for a wide range of pesticides and commodities, including olives and olive oil [13,28].

However, the results in terms of selectivity, sensitivity and degree of confirmation improve remarkably when MS² is applied. GC-MS², using either triple quadrupole in selected reaction monitoring (SRM) or ion-trap (IT) instruments, enables the unambiguous

identification and quantitation of a large number of compounds in complex matrixes [8–12].

As can be seen in Table 2, the results using GC-MS² are excellent for olive-oil samples with LODs below 10 ng/g [47]. Fig. 4 shows the chromatograms obtained in the determination of selected pesticides in an olive-oil sample – spiked at 10 ng/g – by GC-MS² analysis [47]. The extracted chromatograms for each individual compound reveal the high sensitivity of the methodology with remarkably high signal-to-noise ratios at such low concentration levels. The results are distinctly better than those achievable by single GC-MS in SIM mode. The additional MS stage of MS² instruments provides enhanced selectivity, reducing the noise from the matrix and thus improving selectivity and signal-to-noise ratios of analytes. The increase of performance may vary from 10 to 50-fold sensitivity enhancement, depending on the matrix, compound and instruments.

3.2. LC-MS

To date, GC-MS or GC-MS² is the technique of choice for PRA in both olive oil and olives. However, the number of newly authorized pesticides and commercial formulations used in olive groves grows each year, in line with integrated pest-management guidelines. Furthermore, these new substances used are more polar, since these new-generation pesticides are more environmentally friendly than the former non-polar pesticides, which are highly persistent in the environment.

The tendency to apply these new polar compounds has prompted the use of LC-MS as a complementary tool to GC-MS, particularly for compounds not amenable to GC (e.g., a wide range of herbicides widely used in olive groves (viz. amitrole, diuron, diquat, paraquat)). In this scenario, the use of LC-MS becomes mandatory.

In a recent study [48] (See Table 3), for a total of 500 pesticides – selected as the most important in Germany – LC-MS gave better results than GC-MS. Of the 500 compounds tested, 453 were amenable to LC-MS, while only 365 could be analyzed by GC-MS. For the organo-chlorines only, the use of GC-MS has advantages over LC-MS, as shown in Table 3.

There has been scarcely any literature on LC-MS methods for pesticides in olive oil and olives. Barrek et al. [13] proposed the first method using a single quadrupole analyzer in SIM mode to attain LODs typically in the range 40–200 µg/kg. After that, more effective and sensitive LC-MS² methods were reported.

An LC-IT instrument operating in MS² mode was used to determine triazine herbicides and dimethoate at low- µg/kg levels in both olives and olive oil [28]. A

method for the analysis of two non-GC amenable quaternary ammonium herbicides (diquat and paraquat) using a triple quadrupole instrument operating in SRM mode was described recently, obtaining LODs below 3 µg/kg for both compounds. The method was based on the use of an ion-pairing agent (HFBA) to provide adequate chromatographic conditions for both quaternary ammonium salts [33].

There are several reasons to apply LC-MS or LC-MS² for the analyses of pesticides in olives and olive oil. First, the number of pesticides used or of interest in olive groves is increasing daily, and these compounds (mainly herbicides) are more polar so less amenable to analysis by GC-MS. Furthermore, the matrix effects observed by GC-MS in high fat-content commodities are typically stronger than when LC-MS is applied. Moreover, the sensitivity achievable by GC-MS is often unsatisfactory, taking into account the regulations that will be established in future years for pesticide residues in olive oil. For example, the emerging field of “organic food” requires the development of tools to analyze pesticide residues in olive oil with at very low- µg/kg concentration levels (i.e.: 0.5–2 µg/kg). In this sense, LC-MS² methods usually have remarkable analytical features to comply with these requirements [28]).

However, time-of-flight MS (TOF-MS) offers attractive features for the analysis of pesticides in complex matrixes. TOF analyzers are capable of 10,000 or more resolving power (FWHM) [49]. LC-TOF-MS therefore benefits from the high resolving power of signals on the m/z axis, enabling the measurement of accurate masses of ions within mass accuracies approaching Fourier transform MS (FT-MS) instruments [50] when dynamic accurate mass-calibration systems are used.

Accurate mass analysis of ions usually yields the elemental composition of parent and fragment ions, which can be used for unambiguous identification and/or confirmation of a target species (“target analysis”) or to identify unknown or unexpected compounds (“non-target analysis”). LC-TOF-MS has been successfully applied to identification and determination of several classes of pesticides in vegetable samples [51] and recently to the analyses of herbicides residues in olive oil [29], obtaining promising results (Fig. 5). The main advantage of this methodology is the potential to identify and to characterize the most common degradation products of pesticides in food together with unknown or “non-target” unexpected pesticides without using standards *a priori* [50].

The combination of accurate mass analysis from LC- TOF-MS with MS² experiments with complementary MS techniques (i.e. LC-IT-MSⁿ or LC-Q-TOF-MS) will enable the identification of new degradation products of pesticides, which could be relevant, since these compounds often are as toxic as their parent species. This is a potential application that will be further explored in the near future in PRA in olive oil as it has been in other

commodities (e.g., fruits and vegetables) [50,52].

4. Concluding remarks

The development of sample-treatment methodologies for the determination of pesticide residues in matrices with high fat content (such as olives and olive oil) is a demanding task, since even small amounts of co-extracted fat must be removed to keep the chromatographic system in working order. For this reason, clean-up steps must be included in the extraction procedures. In this sense, there is a clear trend towards the development of miniaturized sample-handling methodologies that consume small amounts of organic solvents.

However, multi-residue methods to cover a large number of pesticides are highly desirable, although the different natures, classes and physicochemical properties of pesticides used in olive groves hamper the development of such methodologies.

Different versatile sample-handling strategies that we discussed above (GPC, MSPD and QuEChERS) can circumvent the main problems associated with this kind of matrix and permit development of multi-residue methods when combined with selective and sensitive methodologies based on GC-MS² and LC-MS², which enable the unambiguous identification and quantitation of pesticides that might be present in olive-oil samples at very low concentrations, due to their stability in that matrix. The use of LC-TOF-MS will enable the development of multi-residue methods in olive oil, since the number of compounds to be screened in one run is practically unlimited and, in addition, the scope of TOF methods also includes both non-target and unknown compounds (i.e. degradation products) owing to the resolving power, accurate mass-measurement capabilities and full spectral sensitivity, which make LC-TOF-MS attractive as a tool for identifying non-target or unknown compounds.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge funding support from Junta de Andalucía (Regional Government of Andalucía (Spain) Research Groups FQM 323, AGR 159 and Project FQM- 01463) and Spanish “Ministerio de Educación y Ciencia” (Project BQU-2006-15066 and FPU program scholarship (AP2002-0894)).

References

- [1] US Food and Drug Administration, News, November 2004 (www.fda.gov/bbs/topics/news/2004/NEW01129.html).
- [2] F. Luchetti, Eur. J. Lipid Sci. Technol. 104 (2002) 559.
- [3] Ch. Lentza-Rizos, Grasas Aceites 47 (1996) 392.
- [4] Ch. Lentza Rizos, E.J. Avramides, Rev. Environ. Contam. Toxicol. 141 (1995) 111.
- [5] European Commission, Regulation (EC) N° 396/2005 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 February 2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides in products of plant and animal origin, OJ L 70 (2005) 1.
- [6] European Commission, Regulation (EC) N° 178/2006 of 1 February 2006 amending Regulation (EC) N° 396/2005 of the European Parliament and the Council to establish Annex I listing the food and feed products to which maximum levels for pesticide residue apply, OJ L 178 (2006) 24.
- [7] M. López-Mesas, M. Crespí, Grasas Aceites 51 (2000) 183.
- [8] E. Ballesteros, A. García Sánchez, N. Ramos Martos, J. Chromatogr., A 1111 (2006) 89.
- [9] A. García Sánchez, N. Ramos Martos, E. Ballesteros, Anal. Chim. Acta 558 (2006) 53.
- [10] M. Guardia-Rubio, M.L. Fernández de Córdoba, M.J. Ayora- Cañada, A. Ruiz-Medina, J. Chromatogr., A 1108 (2006) 231.
- [11] M.A. Aramendía, F. Lafont, A. Marinas, J.M. Marinas, J.M. Moreno, J.M. Porras, F.J. Urbano, "Determinación de herbicidas en aceite de oliva mediante GC-MS y/o HPLC-MS", Paper, Symposium Científico-Técnico EXPOLIVA 2005, Jaén, Spain.
- [12] K. Patel, R.J. Fussell, M. Hetmanski, D.M. Goodall, B.J. Keely, J. Chromatogr., A 1068 (2005) 289.
- [13] S. Barrek, O. Paise, M.-F. Grenier-Loustalot, Anal. Bioanal. Chem. 376 (2003) 355.
- [14] M.L. Hopper, J. Chromatogr., A 840 (1999) 93.
- [15] C. Yaguñe, S. Bayarri, P. Conchillo, R. Lázaro, C. Pérez-Arquillé, A. Herrera, A. Ariño, J. Agric. Food Chem. 53 (2005) 5105.
- [16] A. Di Muccio, T. Generali, D.A. Barbini, P. Pelosi, A. Ausili, F. Vergori, S. Girolometti, J. Chromatogr., A 765 (1997) 61.
- [17] L. Rastrelli, K. Totaro, F. De Simona, Food Chem. 79 (2002) 303.
- [18] A. Di Muccio, A. Ausili, R. Dommarco, D.A. Barbini, A. Santilio, F. Vergori, G. De Merulis, L. Sernicola, J. Chromatogr., A 552 (1991) 241.
- [19] A. Ramesh, M. Balasubramanian, Analyst (Cambridge, UK) 123 (1998) 1799.
- [20] C. Tsoutsis, I. Konstantinou, D. Hela, T. Albanis, Anal. Chim. Acta. 573–574 (2006) 216.

- [21] A. Di Muccio, P. Pelosi, D.A. Barbini, T. Generali, S. Girolimetti, P. Stefanelli, A. Leonelli, G. Amándola, L. Vergori, E.V. Fresquet, *J. Chromatogr., A* 833 (1999) 19.
- [22] F.A. Esteve-Turrillas, A. Pastor, M. De la Guardia, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 553 (2005) 50.
- [23] R. Raoux, J.L. Coustille, S. Rambaud, *Oleagineux, Corps Gras, Lipides* 4 (1997) 71.
- [24] E.G. Amvrazi, T.A. Albanis, Determination of various pesticide residues in Greek virgin olive oil by a multi-residue method using different clean up procedures and gas chromatography, in: T.D. Lekkas (Editor), *Proc. 9th Int. Conf. Environ. Sci. Technol.*, University of the Aegean, Rhodes Island, Greece, 2005.
- [25] Ch. Lentza-Rizos, E.J. Avramides, E. Visi, *J. Chromatogr., A* 921 (2001) 297.
- [26] Ch. Lentza-Rizos, E.J. Avramides, F. Cherasco, *J. Chromatogr., A* 912 (2001) 135.
- [27] A.M. Tsatsakis, I.N. Tsakiris, M.N. Tzatzarakis, Z.B. Agourakis, M. Tutudaki, A.K. Alegakis, *Food Addit. Contam.* 20 (2003) 553.
- [28] C. Ferrer, M.J. Gómez, J.F. García-Reyes, I. Ferrer, E.M. Thurman, A.R. Fernández-Alba, *J. Chromatogr., A* 1069 (2005) 183.
- [29] J.F. García-Reyes, C. Ferrer, E.M. Thurman, A.R. Fernández-Alba, I. Ferrer, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 54 (2006) 6493.
- [30] M.A. Aramendía, M. De Juan, F. Lafont, A. Marinas, J.M. Marinas, J.M. Moreno, J.M. Porras, O.M. Sobrino, F.J. Urbano, R. Vilches, "Determinación de amitrol, dimetoato y diuron en aceite de oliva mediante HPLC-EM/EM", Paper, Symposium Científico-Técnico EXPOLIVA 2005, Jaén, Spain.
- [31] G. Dugo, G. Di Bella, L. La Torre, M. Saitta, *Food Control* 16 (2005) 435.
- [32] A.E. Hiskia, M.E. Atmajidou, D.F. Tsiipi, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 46 (1998) 570.
- [33] M.A. Aramendia, V. Borau, F. Lafont, A. Marinas, J.M. Marinas, J.M. Porras, F.J. Urbano, *Food Chem.* 97 (2006) 181.
- [34] P. Cabras, A. Angioni, M. Melis, E.V. Minelli, F.M. Pirisi, *J. Chromatogr., A* 761 (1997) 327.
- [35] R. Sánchez, A. Vázquez, J. Villen-Altamirano, J. Villen, *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 86 (2006) 129.
- [36] R. Sánchez, J.M. Cortes, J. Villén, A. Vázquez, *J. AOAC Int.* 88 (2005) 1255.
- [37] R. Sánchez, A. Vázquez, D. Riquelme, J. Villén, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 51 (2003) 6098.
- [38] R. Sánchez, A. Vázquez, J.C. Andini, J.J. Villén, *J. Chromatogr., A* 1029 (2004) 167.
- [39] J.J. Vreuls, R.J.J. Swen, V.P. Goudriaan, M.A.T. Kerkhoff, G.A. Jongenotter, U.A.Th. Brinkman, *J. Chromatogr., A* 750 (1996) 275.
- [40] G.A. Jongenotter, M.A.T. Kerkhoff, H.C.M. van der Knaap, B.G.M. Vandeginste, *J. High Resol. Chromatogr.* 22 (1999) 17.

- [41] M. Guardia-Rubio, A. Ruiz-Medina, A. Molina-Díaz, M.J. Ayora- Cañada, J. Agric. Food Chem. 54 (2006) 8538.
- [42] E.J. Avramides, "A multi-residue gas chromatographic method for the determination of insecticides in olive fruits", Paper, European Pesticide Residue Workshop (EPRW 2006), Crete, Greece, May 2006.
- [43] M. Anastassiades, S.J. Lehotay, D. Stajnbaher, F.J. Schenck, J. AOAC Int. 86 (2003) 412.
- [44] M. Anastassiades, B. Tsdelen, E. Scherbaum, "New Developments in QuEChERS methodology", Paper, European Pesticide Residue Workshop (EPRW 2006), Crete, Greece, May 2006.
- [45] European Commission, Quality Control Procedures for Pesticide Residues Analyses, SANCO/10232/2006, 24 March 2006 (http://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/protection/resources/qualcontrol_en.pdf).
- [46] European Commission, Decision of 12 August 2002, implementing Council Directive 96/23/EC concerning the performance of analytical methods and the interpretation of results (2002/657/ EC), OJ L 221 (2002) 8.
- [47] C. Ferrer, M.J. Gómez-Ramos, P. Medina, A. Agüera, A.R. Fernández-Alba, "Simple sample preparation strategies for the analysis of pesticides residues in olive oil", Paper, European Pesticide Residue Workshop (EPRW 2004), Stockholm, Sweden, June 2004.
- [48] L. Alder, K. Greulich, G. Kempe, B. Vieth, Mass Spectrom. Rev. 25 (2006) 838.
- [49] S. Lacorte, A.R. Fernández-Alba, Mass Spectrom. Rev. 25 (2006) 866.
- [50] J.F. García-Reyes, A. Molina-Díaz, A.R. Fernández-Alba, Anal. Chem. 79 (2007) 307.
- [51] I. Ferrer, J.F. García-Reyes, A.R. Fernández-Alba, Trends Anal. Chem. 24 (2005) 671.
- [52] J.F. García-Reyes, I. Ferrer, E.M. Thurman, A. Molina-Díaz, A.R. Fernández-Alba, Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom. 19 (2005) 2780.

Figure 1. Average world olive-oil production (1990–2000) [2]

Figure 2. (a) Gel-permeation chromatography (GPC) system for the extraction of pesticides in olive oil, comprising: a set of high-pressure pumps; the columns, where the separation by size/weight is carried out; a fraction collector; and, a detector to monitor the procedure; (b) MSPD extraction procedure; and, (c) QuEChERS procedure

Figure 3. Comparison of GC-MS chromatograms in full-scan mode of olive-oil extracts obtained by MSPD procedure and by GPC using two collection times [28].

Figure 4. Chromatograms corresponding to the GC-MS² analysis of an olive-oil sample spiked with 10 µg/kg of the pesticides studied (terbutylazine, endosulfan I, endosulfan II, oxyfluorfen and endosulfan sulphate [47]).

Figure 5. (a) Total ion chromatogram corresponding to the analysis of a spiked olive-oil sample with herbicides terbuthylazine, simazine and diuron by liquid chromatography electrospray time-of-flight mass spectrometry (LC-TOF-MS). Fortification level: 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. (b) Extracted ion chromatograms of terbuthylazine (b.1), simazine (b.2) and diuron (b.3) using a mass-window width of 40 mDa.

Table 1. Summary of extraction procedures for the determination of pesticides in olive oil and olives				
Analytes	Extraction and clean-up procedures	Determination	Recoveries (%)	Ref.
<i>GPC and related methods</i>				
Multi-residue of 26 pesticides and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons	Liquid-liquid partition with acetonitrile saturated with hexane followed by GPC clean-up	GC-MS ² (CI and EI)	84–110%	[8,9]
Multi-residue of 32 multiclass pesticides (organochlorine, triazines and organophosphorus)	Liquid-liquid partition with acetonitrile saturated with hexane followed by GPC clean-up	GC-ECD GC-TSD GC-MS ²	82–124%	[10]
Simazine, atrazine, propazine, terbuthylazine, duron, oxyfluorfen, norflurazon, diflufenican	Liquid-liquid partition with acetonitrile saturated with hexane followed by clean-up by either GPC or Florisil column	GC-MS ² LC-ESI-QqQ-MS ²	–	[11]
19 organochlorine pesticides	1.25 g olive oil dissolved in 10 ml ethyl acetate:cyclohexane (1:1). Direct extraction/clean-up with GPC	GC-QqQ-MS ² (triple quadrupole in SRM mode)	63–111%	[12]
Multi-residue of 50 multiclass pesticides (e.g., organochlorine, organophosphorus, triazines and pyrethroids)	0.5 g olive oil dissolved in 5 ml THF. Direct extraction and clean-up by GPC.	GC-Q-MS (SIM mode) LC-ESI-Q-MS (SIM mode)	3–99%	[13]
Multi-residue of organochlorine and organophosphorus pesticides	Supercritical fluids extraction. Clean-up with a Florisil cartridge	GC-ECD GC-NPD	0–118%	[14]
<i>Liquid-liquid-SPE-based methods</i>				
Organochlorine, organophosphorus and PCBs	Olive oil dissolved with hexane. Extraction on Extrelut-QE column; followed by SPE clean-up with two cartridges (C ₁₈ and alumina)	GC-NPD GC-ECD GC-MS ²	66–105%	[15]
15 organochlorine pesticides	SPE with two cartridges “on-line” (Extrelut-3 and C ₁₈); clean-up with Florisil column	GC-ECD	53–107%	[16]
18 organophosphorus insecticides	SPE with two cartridges “on-line” (Extrelut-3 and C ₁₈)	GC-NPD	82–110%	[17]
18 organochlorine insecticides	SPE with Extrelut-3 (Kieselghur); clean-up 1 with Florisil column; final clean-up with Extrelut-1 column	GC-ECD	72–104%	[18]
7 pyrethroid insecticides	SPE with graphitized carbon black (GCB)	GC-ECD	94–105%	[19]
Multi-residue of 13 organophosphorus insecticides	Headspace SPME (with PDMS fibers)	GC-FID	80–106%	[20]
Multi-residue of pyrethroids	SPE and clean-up with 2 cartridges “on-line”: Extrelut-3 and a second cartridge mixture of Extrelut 1 + C ₁₈)	GC-ECD	80–111%	[21]
11 pyrethroid insecticides	Liquid-liquid partition with acetonitrile:hexane (1:1) followed by clean-up by SPE using C ₁₈ (500 mg) and alumina (2 g)	GC-MS ²	91–104%	[22]
Organochlorine, organophosphorus and PCBs	Liquid-liquid partition with acetonitrile:dichloromethane 95:5) followed by clean-up by SPE using C ₁₈ and Florisil	GC-ECD GC-NPD	88–105%	[23]
Multi-residue of 30 insecticides (organophosphorus, organochlorine, pyrethroids) and 5 herbicides (triazines)	Liquid-liquid partition with acetonitrile (olive oil dissolved in hexane); clean-up first with an SPE Envicarb cartridge and final step with a normal-phase Diol SPE cartridge	GC-ECD GC-NPD	70–106%	[24]
Endosulfan and 5 pyrethroid insecticides	Two extraction methods: (a) Liquid-liquid partition with acetonitrile (olive oil dissolved in hexane); (b) Mix olive oil with acetonitrile and low-temperature fat removal at –20 °C. Final clean-up with Sep-Pak alumina-N column	GC-ECD	72–91%	[25]

Multi-residue of 17 pesticides (3 triazines and 14 organophosphorus insecticides)	Liquid-liquid partition with acetonitrile followed by low-temperature fat precipitation and removal at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Clean-up with Sep-Pak alumina-N column	GC-NPD	77–104%	[26]
Dimethoate and fenthion	Liquid-liquid partition with acetonitrile saturated with hexane, followed by clean-up using a C_{18} cartridge	GC-Q-MS (SIM mode) GC-NPD	78–84%	[27]
Multi-residue of triazines, organophosphorus, organochlorine and pyrethroids	Preliminary liquid-liquid partition with acetonitrile saturated with petroleum ether followed by MSPD extraction with aminopropyl and clean-up with Florisil	GC-Q-MS (SIM mode) LC-ESI-MS ²	73–130%	[28]
Simazine, atrazine, diuron and terbuthylazine	Preliminary liquid-liquid partition with acetonitrile saturated with petroleum ether followed by MSPD extraction with aminopropyl and clean-up with Florisil	LC-ESI-TOF-MS	81–111%	[29]
<i>Liquid-liquid partitioning and other methods</i>				
Amitrol, dimethoate and diuron	Liquid-liquid partition with 80:20 (v/v) AcN : H_2O with HCOOH 1%. Olive oil dissolved in hexane	LC-ESI (+) QqQ-MS ² (SRM mode)	70–95%	[30]
Dimethoate, parathion-methyl, fenthion, methidathion, parathion-ethyl	Liquid-liquid partition with acetonitrile and centrifugation. No clean-up	GC-FID	78–97%	[31]
15 organophosphorus insecticides	Liquid-liquid partition (twice) (olive oil dissolved in hexane) with acetonitrile saturated with hexane.	GC-NPD GC-FID	73–166%	[32]
Diquat and paraquat	Liquid-liquid partition (twice) (2 g olive oil dissolved in 2 ml hexane) with 2 ml H_2O 5 mM HFBA	LC-ESI (+) QqQ-MS ²	93–99%	[33]
13 organophosphorus insecticides	Liquid-liquid partition (twice) (2 g olive oil dissolved in 2 ml hexane) with 10 ml acetonitrile	GC-NPD	74–118%	[34]
Multiclass pesticides (triazines and organophosphorus)	Extraction and clean-up by on-line coupling (TOTAD interface) of RPLC and GC (RPLC-GC).	RPLC-GC-FID RPLC-GC-NPD	Not available	[35–38]
17 organophosphorus pesticides	Extraction, clean-up and determination by on-line coupling GPC-GC. 1 g olive oil dissolved in AcOEt:cyclohexane; 30 μl injected on GPC-GC	GPC-GC-NPD GPC-GC-FID	83–103%	[39,40]
<i>Extraction procedures for determination of pesticides in olives</i>				
Endosulfan sulfate, diuron and terbuthylazine	Preliminary liquid-liquid partition (twice) with petroleum ether, using a high-speed blender (Ultraturrax). Liquid-liquid partition with acetonitrile saturated with n-hexane. Final clean-up step with GPC	GC-MS ²	82–130%	[41]
Multi-residue of 18 herbicides and insecticides	Liquid-liquid partition with acetonitrile. Low-temperature fat precipitation clean-up, and final clean-up with SepPak cartridge (alumina).	GC-ECD GC-NPD	69–88%	[42]
Triazines, organophosphorus, organochlorine and pyrethroids	Extraction by MSPD using aminopropyl followed by clean-up with Florisil column	GC-Q-MS (SIM mode) LC-ESI-MS ²	81–111%	[28]

Table 2. Analytical parameters obtained with a GC-MS² method for the analysis of selected pesticides in olives and olive oil [47]

	Concentration range (mg/kg)	Linearity (r)		Limit of Detection (1g/kg)		RSD (%) (n = 6)	
		Oil	Olives	Oil	Olives	Oil	Olives
Simazine	0.01–0.5	0.991	0.994	8	12	5.2	7.1
Terbutylazine	0.01–0.5	0.995	0.992	3	5	5.2	5.6
Endosulfan I	0.01–0.5	0.996	0.999	3	5	6.8	4.8
Endosulfan II	0.01–0.5	0.997	0.999	8	15	7.7	5.6
End. Sulfate	0.01–0.5	0.994	0.996	3	4	7.3	7.1
Cypermethrin	0.01–0.5	0.988	0.990	5	7	6.2	6.4
Deltamethrin	0.01–0.5	0.990	0.991	6	10	4.0	5.5

Table 3. Comparative evaluation of the potential of GC-MS and LC-MS for the development of multi-residue methods of pesticides in foodstuffs [48]

Pesticide class	Number of pesticides studied	Not detected by GC-MS	Not detected by LC-MS
Organophosphorus	81	0	1 (Fenclorphos)
Carbamate	43	17	1 (Chlorpropham)
Organochlorine	40	0	33 (all except ^a)
Sulfonyl urea	26	26	0
Triazole	24	1	0
Triazine	23	6	0
Urea	22	16	0
Pyrethroid	19	0	2 ^b
Aryloxyphenoxypropionate	12	4	0
Aryloxyalkanoic acid	10	9	0
Other	200	56	12 ^c
Total	500	135	47

^aOrganochlorine pesticides detected by LC-MS: iprodione, procymidone, endosulfan sulfate, binapacryl, flurochloridone, chlorthiamid and chlorobenzilate.

^bPyrethroids not detected by LC-MS: tefluthrin and transluthrin.

^cOther pesticides not detected by LC-MS: benfluralin, biphenyl, captan, chlorbensid, chlorotalonil, chlorfenapyr, chlorthan-dimethyl, etridiazole, nitrothal-isopropyl, quintozone and tecnazene.